

Plenary statement at the United Nations 69th Commission on Narcotic Drugs (CND) session to the agenda item '5e: Other matters arising from the international drug control treaties'

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Your Excellencies, distinguished delegations, colleagues from civil society:

Thank you for giving me the space. My name is Jitka Nykodemová and I speak in the place of Instituto RIA, a Mexican-based organisation that undertakes high-quality research, highlighting and proposing innovations in order to advocate for public policies within a social justice framework.

Addressing agenda item 5e: 'Other matters arising from the international drug control treaties', I am asking myself: instead of continually reaffirming our commitment to, financial support of, control of compliance with, and enforcement of these treaties in question, shouldn't we, with equal effort and urgency, also be simultaneously and genuinely inquiring 'what claims and values are they based on', and 'what is their relevance to the state of the world and our knowledge as it evolves over time'? As a global community, we state our commitments to certain noble ideals, via declarations of the United Nations and others, while simultaneously conducting a planetary-wide activity which harms them, prevents their thriving or sometimes their very existence. We are waging a worldwide war, enshrined in the conventions of the United Nations, a self-proclaimed peace-building international institution. Some call it a "world drug problem", to be "addressed and countered". Some call it directly a "war on drugs". Framed in this way, it is indeed a fight, a war that is going on, globally and for several decades. Let us restate – a planetary-wide war, truly; maybe not with explosives, but instead subtle, persuasive and continuous. Have we not noticed the contradictions, or are we consciously choosing it? Sasha Shulgin asked in their second book *TIHKAL* "qui bono?", who benefits from the prohibition attitudes to drugs? Indeed who? This we should be asking I truly believe – and not on the sides, but right here where the current regime of drug control, stemming from the treaties in question, originates and is sustained.

It is my second year here at CND and it has been a shock being here. I can't comprehend how many of us who come here for perhaps decades maintain sanity – among the hypocrisy and irrationality of schedules and scheduling, the proclaimed commitments immediately contradicted by their consequences, the blind repetition of vague phrases, sometimes well-sounding, but without meaning anything concrete. Ritualistically and with a near religious fervour, there seems to be an ideological dogma being lived and enacted. I'm confounded that for nearly 70 years we come here, meet, applaud ourselves to work which is obviously failing at large, yet reaffirm our commitments to keep doing the same thing over and over, and keep asking for more money to keep doing the same.

Many means exist to learn on our unique way of life, and each of us should have the sole authority to choose it. To the life learning paths can also belong the use of psychoactive drugs, and they must be – and will be – available for these reasons, and for many others.

I can't stop thinking about what are we afraid of, why this war against drugs, and words of Ann Shulgin, reflecting on the war on drugs in her chapter 'Invasion' in the book *TIHKAL*, keep resonating in mind: "I believe there is an intense, unconscious fear of the hidden depths of the human psyche, and an unacknowledged certainty that the Shadow, the dark side, is indeed the final, terrible, rockbottom truth about the nature of mankind. [...] Until there is a growth of understanding of the Shadow side of us, and realisation that it is possible for that dark aspect to undergo transformation, this fear and hostility towards anything that opens up the human unconscious will continue."

Thank you for your attention.